

Apparent Molar Volumes of L-Serine and L-Threonine in Methanol—Water Mixtures

J. S. SANDHU*, PARAMPAUL KAUR and URMIL KASHYAP

Department of Chemistry, Punjab University, Patiala-147 002

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Apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) of L-serine in water, 10, 20 and 30% (w/w) methanol—water mixtures, and of L-threonine in water, 10, 15 and 20% methanol—water mixtures have been obtained from measurements of density at 25, 35 and 45°, respectively. The limiting values ϕ_v° have been calculated by a linear extrapolation using the least-squares method. These data have been used to derive the solvation number (n_s) of L-serine and L-threonine. The n_s values obtained increase with the addition of methanol for both the amino acids and at all temperatures.

THE importance of amino acids and water in living systems is well known. The apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) of a number of amino acids have been reported at different concentrations¹⁻⁶. However, the dependence of the limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v°) on temperature does not appear to have received adequate attention although such a study is likely to give an insight into the mode of solute—solvent interactions.

In order to understand better the interactions of amino acids with solvents, we have determined the limiting apparent molar volumes and hence the hydration numbers of L-serine and L-threonine in methanol—water mixtures; the survey of literature reveals that no work has been done yet.

Experimental

L-Serine and L-threonine (Sigma, extrapure) were used without further purification. The amino acids were dried in an air-oven at 150° for 1 h, then under vacuum for 24 h and stored in a vacuum desiccator over calcium chloride.

The density measurements were carried out in a thermostatic water-bath ($\pm 0.01^\circ$). The densities of solutions were measured to $\pm 2 \times 10^{-4}$ g cm⁻³ with the aid of a single stem pycnometer of about 14 cm³ capacity. It was calibrated with water; density of water being 0.997 07, 0.994 06, 0.990 25 g cm⁻³ at 25, 35 and 45°, respectively.

Methanol (AnalaR) was purified by standard procedure⁷. All solutions were prepared using double-distilled water. The concentrations were converted to molarities C from the known densities.

Results and Discussion

The densities measured at 25, 35 and 45° as reported elsewhere⁸ have been used to calculate the

apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) of the solute using the relation,

$$\phi_v/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} = \frac{1000(d_0 - d)}{Cd_0} + \frac{M}{d_0} \quad (1)$$

where, d_0 and d are the densities of solvent and solution, respectively, C is the molar concentration and M is the molecular weight of the amino acid. The ϕ_v values of aqueous and aqueous solutions of methanol, as a function of concentration and at three temperatures studied, are given in Tables 1 and 2. Since the trends of variation of ϕ_v as a function of concentration of both the amino acids are found to be similar, only plots in aqueous system and 20% methanol—water mixtures have been shown in Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4. All the plots of ϕ_v against concentration are found to have positive slopes. The limiting values (ϕ_v°) are obtained by linear extrapolation using the least-square fit to the following equation,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^\circ + S_v C \quad (2)$$

where, ϕ_v° is the infinite dilution apparent molar volume and S_v is the experimental slope. The values of ϕ_v° , S_v , and standard errors, σ , are given in Table 3 along with the literature values. The ϕ_v° values obtained for L-serine (61.02 ± 0.04) and L-threonine (77.63 ± 0.07) in aqueous system are in good agreement with those (60.72 ± 0.02 and 76.91 ± 0.01 , respectively) obtained by Ogawa *et al.*⁹. The values of S_v obtained at 298.15 K for L-serine (1.32) and L-threonine (0.68) are also in reasonable agreement with those (1.14 and 0.89, respectively) reported by the same workers. The values of ϕ_v° at temperatures other than 298.15 K could not be compared due to lack of literature data at these temperatures. It is evident from Table 3 that ϕ_v° increases with increase in temperature, for both the amino acids in aqueous and methanol—water mixtures. This increase can be explained on the basis of primary and secondary solvation layers which appear to be formed around the dipolar ions¹⁰. At higher temperatures, the solvent from the secondary solvent

TABLE 1—APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES OF L-SERINE IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND CONCENTRATIONS

% (w/w) Methanol in solvent mixture	25°		35°		45°	
	[Amino acid] C mol dm ⁻³	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹	[Amino acid] C mol dm ⁻³	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹	[Amino acid] C mol dm ⁻³	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹
0	0.074 38	61.04	0.074 15	61.35	0.073 87	61.70
	0.148 14	61.26	0.147 69	61.71	0.147 13	61.85
	0.197 23	61.36	0.196 64	61.63	0.195 89	61.64
	0.246 03	61.39	0.245 28	61.67	0.244 34	61.82
	0.295 25	61.40	0.292 85	61.68	0.291 73	61.82
	0.341 68	61.51	0.340 64	61.77	0.339 36	61.81
	0.435 29	61.60	0.433 96	61.84	0.432 31	62.00
	0.530 93	61.76	0.529 35	61.88	0.527 37	61.95
	0.621 69	61.79	0.619 84	61.90	0.617 45	62.18
10	0.088 79	60.80	0.088 48	61.07	0.088 11	61.25
	0.174 54	60.80	0.173 93	61.03	0.173 20	61.33
	0.254 49	60.74	0.253 58	61.52	0.252 54	61.29
	0.335 43	60.97	0.334 27	61.21	0.332 85	61.53
	0.428 19	61.09	0.426 71	61.35	0.424 90	61.64
	0.522 34	61.34	0.520 54	61.52	0.518 30	61.95
20	0.052 30	60.56	0.052 07	60.49	0.051 81	60.68
	0.087 42	60.66	0.087 04	60.75	0.086 59	60.90
	0.132 72	60.42	0.132 13	60.98	0.131 46	61.24
	0.181 61	60.69	0.180 82	60.86	0.179 89	61.10
	0.237 86	60.90	0.236 83	60.87	0.235 61	61.23
	0.330 32	61.00	0.328 90	60.97	0.327 19	61.51
	0.421 71	61.11	0.419 87	61.29	0.417 69	61.76
	0.070 93	61.53	0.070 55	61.46	0.070 08	61.83
	0.086 02	61.28	0.085 90	61.57	0.084 98	61.98
0.094 95	61.66	0.094 44	61.17 ^a	0.093 84	61.72	
0.130 59	61.69	0.129 88	61.72	0.129 02	62.05	
0.178 69	61.91	0.177 72	62.01	0.176 56	62.22	
0.206 41	62.05	0.205 30	61.95	0.203 96	61.12 ^a	
0.234 04	61.90	0.232 77	62.02	0.231 24	62.43	
0.246 55	62.11	0.245 23	61.98	0.243 62	62.41	
0.300 32	62.29	0.298 71	62.19	0.296 75	62.60	

^a Values not taken for least-square fit.

TABLE 2—APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES OF L-THREONINE IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND CONCENTRATIONS

% (w/w) Methanol in solvent mixture	25°		35°		45°	
	[Amino acid] C mol dm ⁻³	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹	[Amino acid] C mol dm ⁻³	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹	[Amino acid] C mol dm ⁻³	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹
0	0.049 91	77.47	0.049 76	77.78	0.049 57	77.51 ^a
	0.089 07	77.02 ^a	0.088 80	77.12 ^a	0.088 46	77.37 ^a
	0.099 66	77.30	0.099 37	77.82	0.098 99	77.95
	0.147 76	77.32	0.147 31	77.83	0.146 75	77.97
	0.188 51	77.81	0.187 96	77.71	0.187 24	78.01
	0.234 78	77.32	0.234 09	77.80	0.233 20	78.00
	0.309 25	77.30	0.308 33	77.81	0.307 16	78.11
	0.348 98	77.86	0.347 95	77.91	0.346 63	78.11
	0.377 20	77.89	0.376 09	77.92	0.374 66	78.19
	0.422 10	77.87	0.420 87	77.90	0.419 25	78.21
10	0.049 07	75.06	0.048 90	75.37	0.048 70	75.50
	0.087 58	75.51 ^a	0.087 28	74.91 ^a	0.086 91	75.27 ^a
	0.116 52	75.21	0.116 12	75.49	0.115 63	75.61
	0.145 33	74.85 ^a	0.144 83	75.30 ^a	0.144 23	74.99 ^a
	0.185 45	75.32	0.184 80	75.75	0.184 03	75.71
	0.231 00	75.29	0.230 19	75.92	0.229 25	75.69
	0.304 35	75.44	0.303 26	76.10	0.302 03	75.92
	0.325 64	75.38	0.324 47	76.10	0.323 15	75.95
	0.376 87	75.46	0.375 49	76.34	0.373 86	75.99

(Table 2 contd.)

15	0.058 01	71.86 ^a	0.057 78	71.78 ^a	0.057 53	73.30 ^a
	0.071 86	72.19	0.071 57	72.57	0.071 26	73.82
	0.086 84	72.35	0.086 48	72.50	0.086 11	73.92
	0.134 99	72.51	0.134 44	72.61	0.133 85	74.09
	0.180 53	72.61	0.179 80	72.59	0.179 00	74.12
	0.229 14	72.79	0.228 22	72.71	0.227 19	74.30
	0.265 09	72.79	0.264 03	72.70	0.262 83	74.31
	0.304 82	73.01	0.303 62	72.77	0.302 22	74.32
	0.329 74	73.10	0.328 46	72.80	0.326 93	74.40
	20	0.050 36	70.36	0.050 14	71.26	0.049 88
0.057 63		70.31	0.057 37	71.56	0.057 08	71.48 ^a
0.071 39		70.03 ^a	0.071 07	70.97 ^a	0.070 71	71.28 ^a
0.086 26		70.50	0.085 88	71.51	0.085 44	71.79
0.134 11		70.59	0.133 51	71.60	0.132 83	71.94
0.179 38		70.64	0.178 57	71.65	0.177 66	72.04
0.227 72		70.66	0.226 68	71.69	0.225 52	72.11
0.263 47		70.70	0.262 27	71.68	0.260 92	72.18
0.300 15		70.79	0.298 77	71.80	0.297 23	72.22

^a Values not taken for least-square fit.

Fig. 1. Plot of apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) vs concentration (C) of L-serine in water at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K.

Fig. 2. Plot of apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) vs concentration (C) of L-threonine in water at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K.

Fig. 3. Plot of apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) vs concentration (C) of L-serine in 20% (w/w) of methanol-water at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K.

layers is released to the bulk resulting in the expansion of the solution more rapidly than the pure solvent¹¹.

Since the main object of this work is the study of solute-solvent interactions, partial molar volume at infinite dilution (\bar{V}^0) is the property which has more interest. The partial molar volume is related to ϕ_v by

$$\bar{V} = \phi_v + C \left(\frac{\partial \phi_v}{\partial C} \right) \quad (3)$$

Experimentally, when ϕ_v is plotted against C and extrapolated to zero concentration the apparent molar volume becomes equal to partial molar volume, i.e. $\phi_v^0 = \bar{V}^0$. In order to ascertain the

Fig. 4. Plot of apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) vs concentration (C) of L-threonine in 20% (w/w) of methanol-water at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K.

influence of the added methanol on ϕ_v^0 of the amino acids, ϕ_v^0 values have been used to estimate the partial volumes of transfer ($\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$) using the relation,

$$\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0 = \phi_v^0(\text{M.S.}) - \phi_v^0(\text{W}) \quad (4)$$

where, $\phi_v(\text{M.S.})$ and $\phi_v(\text{W})$ are the apparent molar volumes at infinite dilution in mixed solvent and in pure water, respectively. The limiting partial molar volumes of transfer ($\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$) at three temperatures have been plotted against molarity of methanol in Fig. 5.

The thermodynamic transfer functions of these amino acids are not a result of the changes in the acid or base dissociation constants of the zwitterionic amino acids in the mixed solvents. This is evident from the fact that the dissociation constants of amino acids are very small and change little in aqueous alcohol mixtures^{1,2}.

The transfer functions may be interpreted in terms of water structure making or breaking effects of the solutes, as has been postulated by Frank and Evans^{1,3}. From Table 3 it can be seen that there is decrease in ϕ_v^0 values of both the amino acids as the percentage of methanol increases. The decrease is evident at all temperatures and upto 20% (w/w) of methanol. The ϕ_v^0 in case of L-serine increases after 20% (w/w) of methanol, thereby showing minimum around this concentration of methanol which is the region of maximum structure enhancement. Such a conclusion is in accordance with the findings of other workers^{14,15}. The decrease in ϕ_v^0 (Table 3) and the negative $\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$ (Table 3) of both the amino acids upto 20% (w/w) methanol thus arise from increase in $V_{\text{electrostriction}}^0$ ($V_{\text{elct.}}^0$), in the presence of

TABLE 3—LIMITING APPARENT MOLAR VOLUME (ϕ_v^0) OF L-SERINE AND L-THREONINE IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Amino acid	% (w/w) Methanol in solvent mixture	Temp. °C	ϕ_v^0 cm ³ mol ⁻¹	S_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹ dm ³	σ cm ³ mol ⁻¹
L-Serine	0	25	61.02 (60.72 ± 0.02) ^a	1.32 (1.14) ^a	0.04
		35	61.45	0.82	0.06
		45	61.61	0.78	0.06
	10	25	60.70	0.71	0.15
		35	60.75	1.78	0.14
		45	61.08	1.32	0.07
	20	25	60.42	1.68	0.09
		35	60.56	1.58	0.10
		45	60.67	2.62	0.09
	30	25	61.20	3.61	0.10
		35	61.32	3.01	0.07
		45	61.57	3.56	0.07
L-Threonine	0	25	77.63 (76.91 ± 0.01) ^a	0.68 (0.89) ^a	0.07
		35	77.74	0.37	0.04
		45	77.85	0.84	0.02
	10	25	75.05	1.13	0.04
		35	75.20	2.96	0.04
		45	75.41	1.57	0.04
	15	25	72.03	3.18	0.04
		35	72.45	1.02	0.08
		45	73.75	2.08	0.05
	20	25	70.30	1.66	0.04
		35	71.36	1.44	0.07
		45	71.66	1.98	0.04

^a Ref. 9.

Fig. 5. Plot of $\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^{\circ}$ of L-serine (A) and L-threonine (B) vs molarity of methanol at (○) 298.15, (●) 308.15 and (Δ) 318.15 K.

where, \bar{V}_{int}° is the intrinsic partial molar volume of amino acid and \bar{V}_{elect}° is the electrostriction partial molar volume due to solvation of the amino acid. The values of \bar{V}_{int}° are calculated by the relation,

$$\bar{V}_{int}^{\circ} = \left(\frac{0.7}{0.634} \right) \bar{V}_{cryst}^{\circ} \quad (6)$$

using \bar{V}_{cryst}° values determined by Berlin and Pallash¹⁷. The values of \bar{V}_{elect}° are calculated from the values of \bar{V}_{int}° using equation (5) and are presented in Table 4. The decrease in volume due to electrostriction has been related to the number of water molecules (n_s) solvated to amino acids by the equation,

$$\bar{V}_{elect}^{\circ} = n_s (\bar{V}_E^{\circ} - \bar{V}_1^{\circ}) \quad (7)$$

where, \bar{V}_E° is the molar volume of electrostricted water and \bar{V}_1° is the molar volume of bulk water. Using the value¹⁶ of $(\bar{V}_E^{\circ} - \bar{V}_1^{\circ}) \approx -3.3 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for electrolytic solution, the n_s values are estimated (Table 4). From Table 4 it can be seen that the solvation number increases with the addition of methanol for both the amino acids and at all temperatures. This is in conformity with the earlier observation that in the presence of methanol there is increase in electrostriction and thus solvation. There is a decrease in solvation number at higher temperatures, however, the decrease is not significant. The decreasing trend shows that solvation is reduced at higher temperatures.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF \bar{V}_{elect}° AND SOLVATION NUMBER (n_s) FOR L-SERINE AND L-THREONINE IN WATER AND METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Amino acid	% (w/w) Methanol	\bar{V}_{elect}° (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)			n_s (ml mol ⁻¹)		
		25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°
L-Serine	0	12.32	11.89	11.73	3.7	3.6	3.5
	10	12.64	12.59	12.26	3.8	3.8	3.7
	20	12.92	12.78	12.67	3.9	3.9	3.8
	30	12.14	12.02	11.77	3.7	3.6	3.6
L-Threonine	0	10.11	10.00	9.89	3.1	3.0	3.0
	10	12.69	12.54	12.33	3.8	3.8	3.7
	15	15.71	15.29	13.99	4.8	4.6	4.2
	20	17.44	16.38	16.08	5.3	5.0	4.9

co-solvent. Thus the electrostriction effect which brings about the diminution in the volume of the solvent caused by the electric fields of the dipolar-solutes is increased in the mixed solvent as compared with that in pure water.

The limiting apparent molar volume data have also been used to calculate the solvation number (n_s) of both the amino acids by the procedure given by Millerio *et al.*¹⁶. Following this, the solvation numbers (n_s) can be calculated from the partial molar volume (\bar{V}°)

$$\bar{V}_{\text{amino acid}}^{\circ} = \bar{V}_{int}^{\circ} + \bar{V}_{elect}^{\circ} \quad (5)$$

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